

Impact of Task, Cognitive, and Relational Job Crafting on Faculty Organizational Commitment: The Mediating Role of Person-Job Fit

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Abstract

The primary aim of this study was to explore the influence of task, cognitive, and relational job crafting on enhancing faculty members' organizational commitment. The study also seeks to assess the intervening role of person-job fit. The respondents of the study comprised 454 faculty members from various universities across Northern India. Descriptive statistics were analyzed using SPSS 23 version, and PLS-SEM was utilized to test the structural relationship and validate the research hypotheses. The findings demonstrated that all three facets of job crafting had a significant favorable influence on faculty organizational commitment. Furthermore, the relationship between all the three aspects of job crafting and faculty organizational commitment was found to be partially mediated by person job fit. The study indicates that allowing flexibility to employees with respect to tailoring their societal, task, and perceptible precincts of their jobs to better align with their preferences, passions, and interests, can improve their job meaningfulness and identity at work. This in turn, leads to more positive organizational results.

Keywords: Empirical, Task Crafting, Cognitive Crafting, Relational Crafting, Organizational Commitment, Person-job fit.

1. Introduction

Employees redesign their own work by altering the requirements of their roles, through a practice of "job crafting." The ability to tailor a job to a person's abilities, values, motivations, and passion is something that employees take advantage of. Employees at the individual and group level customize their job roles by engaging in a proactive bottom-up approach known as "job crafting". This approach involves altering how jobs are perceived, carried out, and interacted with in ways that promote job satisfaction and involvement (Bakker et al., 2004; De Beer et al., 2016; Wrzesniewski & Dutton, 2001). Jobs can be crafted in two distinct ways. First, employees can modify the task-oriented boundaries of their roles (by altering the physical parameters of the job), interpersonal-oriented (through shifting the manner or extent of social interaction), and cognitive-oriented (by changing the perception of work (Wrzesniewski & Dutton, 2001). Wrzesniewski and Dutton, recognized as the pioneering authors of this bottom-up method in job design theory, initially proposed the notion of job crafting in 2001. The second approach to this theory involves employees striking a balance amongst the requirements and resources of their jobs, enabling them to modify, adapt, or reorganize their positions (Tims et al., 2012). Tims et al., (2012) established the concept underlying the theory of job demands and resources. Crafting a job according to them is done by increasing challenging job demands (adding new challenging tasks), reducing deterring job demands (making work less intense emotionally and mentally), increasing social job resources (building relationships with superiors and coworkers),

and elevating structural job resources (opportunity for development and learning new things at work). Among these two conceptualizations of job crafting, abundant research has been done on job crafting by taking into consideration the four dimensions as suggested by the JD-R model (De Beer et al., 2016; Gordon et al., 2015; Mäkikangas et al., 2016; Petrou et al., 2012; Siddiqi, 2015; Tims et al., 2013; Zahoor, 2018; Zito et al., 2019). While most studies have used the JD-R model's dimensions to measure job crafting, limited research has examined job crafting through the original framework proposed by Wrzesniewski & Dutton, (2001). Moreover, there is ample research that has revealed job crafting as a significant antecedent in predicting various positive outcomes like job satisfaction, job engagement, job performance, organizational citizenship behavior, and meaningfulness of work (De Beer et al., 2016; Karollah et al., 2020; Petrou et al., 2012; Siddiqi, 2015; Tims et al., 2015; Wrzesniewski et al., 2013). However, the relationship between job crafting and organizational commitment remains underexplored, particularly in the educational sector (Ghitulescu, 2006; Iqbal, 2016; H. Kim et al., 2018; Li et al., 2021; McNaughtan et al., 2022; Noesgaard & Jørgensen, 2023). While some studies have focused on teachers, but they primarily targeted primary school level teachers in the USA and Italy, leaving room for further investigation in the Indian higher education context (Ingusci et al., 2016; Leana et al., 2009). In addition, studies like Moulik and Giri (2022) have demonstrated that person-job fit mediates the relationship between increasing social job resources and the affective commitment among IT professionals in India, though this research only examined relational crafting. Similarly, Li et al., (2021) and Abbas et al., (2022) explored person-job fit as an intervening variable in the association between job crafting and outcomes of job satisfaction and organizational commitment. However, it is crucial to evoke that the studies has conceptualized job crafting on the basis of the JD-R model. Given this background, there is a need to revisit the original job crafting concept proposed by Wrzesniewski & Dutton, (2001), and unveil the relationship of each dimension - physical , social , and cognitive crafting-with organizational commitment. The primary objective of this study is to find out the relationship between the three dimensions of job crafting and the organizational commitment of faculty members working in various universities in Northern India. Furthermore, the present study will contribute to the existing literature by exploring the role of person-job fit as a mediator variable in the relationship between the three facets of job crafting and the work commitment of faculty members. This research will be one of the earliest to examine the mediating role of person-job fit in the relationship between task, relational, and cognitive crafting and organizational commitment.

2. Review of Literature

2.1. Task Crafting and Organizational Commitment

The theory of job crafting was extended from individual job crafting to collaborative job crafting by Leana et al. (2009). Collaborative crafting involves crafting the precincts of a job by workers who work together as a team. However, at both individual and team levels, they focused only on crafting the task boundaries of jobs. According to Berg et al., (2013), task crafting may entail adjusting, expanding, or decreasing the responsibilities specified in our formal job description. This kind of craftsmanship may also entail altering the character of some duties or allocating different amounts of time to what we already accomplish. Leana et al. (2009) revealed a favorable effect of collaborative task crafting on the commitment of teachers and aides towards their schools. The research findings indicate that employees exhibit increased commitment to their employment and display a decreased propensity to sever ties with their respective organizations when they redesign the parameters of their roles in accordance with their personal conceptions of their tasks and the most optimal approach to accomplishing them. This is because, either individually or collectively, the tasks have been modified, at least somewhat, to better fit the employees. In consonance with the above study, Cheng et al., (2016) also measured job crafting based on the basis of two constructs framed by Leana et al. in (2009). According to the findings, tour leaders' organizational commitment has a substantial positive correlation with job crafting at both the individual and team level. Kim & Lee,(2016) also demonstrated a positive association amongst task crafting and job commitment of sales consultants working in diverse organizations in Korea. The study contended that organizations should allow employees to actively engross in initiating job crafting behaviors at their workplace to keep them motivated and committed. Further , Ghitulescu, (2006) study on autonomous teams working in manufacturing organizations found a robust positive association between task crafting and organizational commitment. From the above-cited literature, the current study posits the ensuing hypothesis:

H1: Task Crafting positively impacts Organizational Commitment of faculty members.

2.2. Relational Crafting and Organizational Commitment

Relational crafting entails alterations to the working environment's interpersonal interactions. Building and/or preserving relationships with coworkers, minimizing or eluding contact with others, and investing time with favored people are all examples of this type of work crafting (Wrzesniewski & Dutton, 2001). Building relationships with others enables workers to engage in more gratifying and supportive interactions, which fulfills their sense of belonging (Vogel et al., 2016). The qualitative case study conducted by Noesgaard and Jorgensen, (2023) has revealed relational crafting as a significant precursor to organizational commitment. The study's findings have revealed that relational crafting promotes the emotional, continuous, and normative commitment of service personnel employed in software firms, which ultimately exerts a positive impact on retention. McNaughtan et al., (2022), after conducting an empirical study on faculty members, also revealed a substantial correlation between work commitment and relational crafting. The study contended that faculty members would be more dedicated and perhaps more productive if they were allowed to vigorously shape the social and interpersonal precincts of their job. Further, Kim & Lee, (2016) found that crafting relational boundaries of the job positively affected the work commitment of sales consultants. Crafting interpersonal relationships at work had a noteworthy positive influence on increasing the commitment of sales consultants by way of increasing the perception level of salespeople towards identification with their organization, which in turn reduced their turnover. Based on the research mentioned above, the study assumes the following presumption

H2: Relational Crafting positively impacts Organizational Commitment of faculty members.

2.3. Cognitive Crafting and Organizational Commitment

Wrzesniewski & Dutton (2001), has defined cognitive crafting as the process of altering one's perspective of their work in a way that makes it more evocative. It has to do with how hard a worker tries to understand and perceive their job in a holistic way (Kirkendall, 2013; Wrzesniewski et al., 2013). Studies have indicated that when workers chip in crafting the perceptive frontiers of their job by way of recognizing their job as having a significant impact on others, by way of perceiving their job helping them to achieve the purpose of their life, it increases employee job satisfaction and meaningfulness (Kim et al., 2018; Wrzesniewski & Dutton, 2001). The results of the study by Ghitulescu, (2006) has demonstrated that cognitive crafting has a noteworthy influence on increasing the commitment of employees working in both the manufacturing and service sectors of the USA. A recent investigation on faculty members of various universities in USA has also exhibited the significant favorable effect of cognitive crafting on increasing the commitment level of faculty members (McNaughtan et al., 2022). Moreover, a qualitative longitudinal study by Noesgaard and Jørgensen, (2023) suggested that employees who are engrossed in crafting the cognitive aspects of their jobs are more likely to show high affective, normative, and continuance commitment towards the particular organization they work for. With the above mentioned literature as a foundation, the current study puts forth the subsequent hypothesis:

H3: Cognitive Crafting positively impacts Organizational Commitment of Faculty members.

2.4. Job Crafting, Organizational Commitment, and Person-Job Fit

Person-job fit is defined as the orientation of a person's personality, aptitudes, and capabilities with their employment (Iqbal, 2016). The alignment of a person's capabilities with the demands and constraints of their job (the demands-abilities fit) or their requirements with the resources provided to them at work (the needs-supplies fit) is referred to as the "person-job fit" (Edwards, 1991). Therefore, finding the right individuals with the proper talents and traits for the right jobs is what is meant by "person-job fit." According to the literature, employees at work can acquire a better fit with their work when they actively indulge in altering the features of their duties (i.e., job crafting). Tims et al., (2015) concentrated on the effects of crafting a job on both the demands and capabilities fit (DA) and requirements and supply fit (NS). It was anticipated that employees would value these employment traits to the point where they would take on more tasks or look for chances to grow personally (i.e., craft their job). The three-wave research study results demonstrated a substantial favorable effect of job crafting on the experienced DA and NS fit, showing that a job that is tailored to an individual's knowledge, skills, abilities, and needs will have more resources, perplexing job demands, and fewer impeding job demands. The findings of the study of Moulik and Giri (2022), demonstrated that increasing the social and relational boundaries of jobs has a favorable relationship with person-job fit. The results further revealed a significant effect of person-job fit on the commitment of 297 IT and ITES employees at the affective level working in diverse industries in India. In addition to this,

the results of the study demonstrated that the association between affective organizational commitment and seeking out social resources was mediated by person-job fit. The study concluded that crafting relational boundaries for jobs aids in matching the employee with the position and achieving desired organizational results. Among knowledge workers, social resource crafting is a strategy for overcoming job demands and achieving perceived job congruence. Another recent study by Abbas et al.(2022) found that person-job fit fully acted as the mediator in the relationship among all four dimensions of job crafting and organizational commitment of personnel working in the food and beverage departments of various five star hotels in Egypt. Wong & Tetrick, (2017) had primarily focused on older workers at work. They have emphasized that the bottom-up approach of shaping task, social, and cognitive limits of the job at work can improve the person-job misfit of older workers whose motives, abilities, and competencies change after ageing leading to the person-job misfit among the older workforce. They have specifically stressed the cognitive aspect of crafting, as it provides workers with an additional tool to develop meaningful work identities and prioritizes job requirements that are relevant to them personally for additional primary job-making. Another empirical study conducted by Li et al. (2021) on 397 Chinese employees also found cognitive crafting had a momentous influence on the person-job fit of older workers, while task and relational crafting were found to exert a substantial impact on person-job fit among young employees. The study also demonstrated that the association among all three aspects of job crafting and work satisfaction is mediated by person-job fit. Additionally, Farzaneh et al.(2014) revealed that person-job fit has a strong correlation with the organizational commitment of employees, which in turn positively impacts the citizenship behavior of employees working for a gas company in Iran. Further, Widodo et al, (2020) conducted research involving 180 government employees in Indonesia, discovering a positive correlation between person-job fit and their commitment levels. The study suggests that when employees try to increase their affinity for their personal aptitudes, skills, likings, needs, and job requirements, it ultimately increases their commitment at work and improves performance. From the above studies, it is quite clear that crafting physical, interpersonal, and cognitive boundaries of the job helps employees increase their fit with their duties, which ultimately increases their commitment level. Thus, the study posits the following hypotheses

H4: The relationship between faculty members' organizational commitment and task crafting is mediated by person-job fit.

H5: The relationship between faculty member's organizational commitment and relational crafting is mediated by person-job fit.

H6: The relationship between faculty member's organizational commitment and cognitive crafting is mediated by person-job fit.

Figure 1: Proposed Model of the study

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Participants and Sample Design

The respondents or participants of the study comprised the academic staff (Professors, Associate Professors, Assistant Professors, and Lecturers) working in various universities in Northern India. Data was collected for the final analysis using convenience sampling. A total of 500 faculty members across all ten sample universities were contacted for the present study. The faculty members were contacted by mailing questionnaires to their respective email addresses. Out of 500 faculty members, only 461 responded, representing a response rate of 92%. After examining the data, seven cases were found to have missing demographic responses. Researchers propose that missing data more than 5% can lead to biased outcomes (Riedel, 2005). The missing response in the current study account for only 1.52 %, therefore eliminating these cases would not alter the representativeness of the sample, given the data is missing at random. Thus, the sample for the final study was restricted to 454 usable responses.

3.2. Measurement Instrument

All constructs were evaluated using a five-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." The JCS scale, that was developed by Slemp & Vella-Brodrick, (2013), was utilized to measure job crafting . Task crafting was measured using four items, relational crafting was measured using four items, and cognitive crafting was measured using 5 items. The JCS scale has good consistency and has been employed recently to access the construct of job crafting in the education sector (McNaughtan et al., 2022). Person-job fit was accessed using eight items derived from the study of Brkich et al. (2002). The study assessed organizational commitment by using eight items derived from the scale of Mowday et al. (1979). Along with these twenty-nine items, questions relating to the demographic profile of participants, such as gender, age, designation, and work experience, was also obtained. The measurement items are shown in appendix I.

4. Results

4.1. Participant Demographics

The demographic data presented in table 1 provides a detailed breakdown of the gender, designation, work experience, and age distribution among a sample population. The gender distribution is heavily skewed towards males, who make up 69.6% (316 individuals) of the population, compared to 30.4% (138 individuals) who are female. This indicates a significant gender disparity in the group. In terms of professional designation, most of the participants are Assistant Professors, accounting for 54.8% (249 individuals) of the sample, followed by Associate Professors at 18.9% (86 individuals), Lecturers at 14.8% (67 individuals), and Professors at 11.5% (52 individuals). This suggests that most individuals in this group are in the early to mid-stages of their academic careers, with fewer at the senior levels. When examining work experience, over half of the participants (55.3%, 251 individuals) have between 0-10 years of experience, indicating a relatively young workforce. Those with 11-20 years of experience represent 28.4% (129 individuals), while those with over 20 years of experience make up 16.3% (74 individuals). Age distribution is consistent with the work experience data; the largest age group is 30-35 years (37.4%, 170 individuals), followed by 36-40 years (21.6%, 98 individuals), and 41-45 years (18.9%, 86 individuals), with 22.0% (100 individuals) being above 45 years. This age and experience distribution highlights a predominance of younger academics in the sample, which aligns with the high percentage of Assistant Professors and early-career professionals.

Table 1: Participant demographics

Demographic criteria	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	316	69.6
	Female	138	30.4
Designation	Professors	52	11.5
	Associate Professors	86	18.9
	Assistant Professors	249	54.8

	Lecturers	67	14.8
Work Experience	0-10 years	251	55.3
	11-20 years	129	28.4
	Above 20 years	74	16.3
Age	30-35 years	170	37.4
	36-40 years	98	21.6
	41-45 years	86	18.9
	Above 45 years.	100	22.0

4.2. Assessment of study model

The evaluation of the model was done in two stages viz., measurement model followed by structural model assessment using Smart PLS 4 (Ringle et al., 2014). The initial analysis included the measurement model assessment, which was done by evaluating the model’s validity and reliability, then structural model assessment of path relationships was conducted to support the put-out hypotheses.

4.3. Evaluation of Measurement Model: the measurement model of the study is displayed in figure 2. The assessment of indicator consistency in the measurement model is accomplished through an examination of the factor loadings of each item. A measurement model achieves a desirable level of indicator reliability when the loading estimates for each item fall between .5 and .7 (Hair et al., 2011). Through analysis, it was determined that all indicators within the measurement model displayed loadings exceeding .7 with a range of values between .757 and .901. Therefore, all items utilized in this study exhibited acceptable indicator reliability. Furthermore, the two most commonly used techniques for evaluating a model’s internal consistency reliability are Cronbach’s alpha and composite reliability (CR). According to Hair et al. (2011) a model is said to have achieved adequate internal consistency reliability when both reliability values are above .70. The values displayed in Table 2 clearly show that both the composite reliability and Cronbach’s alpha of all the constructs are above the threshold value of .70, thereby indicating sufficient internal consistency.

Figure 2: Measurement model

Table 2: Measurement Model Parameters

Constructs	Items	Factor loadings	Cronbach's alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted
Task crafting (TC)	TC1	.877	.863	.865	.710
	TC2	.874			
	TC3	.804			
	TC4	.812			
Relational crafting (RC)	RC1	.858	.845	.846	.684
	RC2	.844			
	RC3	.805			
	RC4	.799			
Cognitive crafting (CC)	CC1	.823	.881	.884	.677
	CC2	.821			
	CC3	.849			
	CC4	.804			
	CC5	.817			
Person Job fit (PJF)	PJF1	.840	.946	.947	.726
	PJF2	.886			
	PJF3	.861			
	PJF4	.835			
	PJF5	.824			
	PJF6	.834			
	PJF7	.853			
	PJF8	.880			
Organisational commitment(OC)	OC1	.901	.922	.924	.648
	OC2	.788			
	OC3	.800			
	OC4	.779			
	OC5	.757			
	OC6	.762			
	OC7	.822			
	OC8	.821			

After analyzing the reliability of the constructs, the next step was to provide for the validity of the measurement instrument, which was assessed through convergent and discriminant validity. For convergent validity establishment, it is necessary to ensure that the AVE value is equal to or exceeds the prescribed threshold of .50 (Fornell & Larcker 1981). This pertains to the degree to which multiple tries aimed at measuring the identical construct are in concurrence (Bagozzi et al., 1991). The results provided in the table 2 depict that all the constructs AVE values are greater than the suggested limit of 0.5, thus providing for the establishment of convergent validity.

Finally, discriminant validity was conducted using heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) ratio instead of Fornell and Larcker criteria, as HTMT ratio provides better results in case of PLS-SEM (Henseler, 2015). The thresholds for HTMT has been

debated in previous works. While Kline, (2011) advocated for a criterion of .85 or below, some researchers supported a more liberal threshold of .90 or lower. The results exhibited in Table 3, advise that the HTMT ratio is below the required threshold of .90, thereby establishing discriminant validity.

Table 3: Discriminant Validity

	HTMT Ratio				
	CC	OC	PJF	RC	TC
CC					
OC	.624				
PJF	.589	.747			
RC	.468	.601	.556		
TC	.594	.732	.662	.522	

4.4. Structural Model Assessment

Before assessing the path relationships in a structural model, the assessment of multicollinearity is necessary. The multicollinearity of the constructs is frequently assessed using the variance inflation factor (VIF). Critical collinearity difficulties among the constructs are indicated by VIF values of 5 or above (Hair et al., 2017). However, according to Hair et al. (2019), collinearity problems can also arise at lower VIF values, like 3. All of the constructs' VIF values, as shown in table 4, are less than 3, which suggests that multicollinearity is not present.

Table 4: Collinearity statistics

	CC	OC	PJF	RC	TC
Cognitive crafting (CC)					
Organizational commitment (OC)		1.572	1.446		
Person job fit (PJF)		1.899			
Relational crafting (RC)		1.420	1.316		
Task crafting (TC)		1.754	1.506		

After verifying the model's reliability, validity and multicollinearity, the evaluation of the proposed relationships was examined using PLS-SEM in Smart-PLS 4. The relationship among constructs is shown in figure 3. The results displayed in table 5 clearly reveal that all the dimensions of job crafting (task $\beta = .258$, $t = 5.409$, $p = 0.000^{**}$, relational $\beta = 0.160$, $t = 3.773$, $p = 0.000^{**}$, and cognitive crafting $\beta = 0.158$, $t = 3.441$, $p = 0.001^{**}$) are having a significant positive impact on the organizational commitment of faculty members. Thus, supporting H1-H3 hypotheses.

Figure 3: Structural model

Table 5: Structural path analysis results

Paths	Beta Coefficients (β)	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values
CC -> OC	0.158	0.046	3.441	0.001
RC-> OC	0.160	0.042	3.773	0.000
TC->OC	0.258	0.052	5.409	0.000
R²				
Organizational commitment (OC)	.614			
Person job fit (PJF)	0.473			

4.5. Model fit assessment

According to Sarstedt et al., (2020), the predictive capability is used to establish model fit in PLS-SEM. The coefficient of determination (R^2) and predictive relevance (Q^2) was used to establish the predictive capability of the model (Hair et al., 2017). The predictive relevance of the model was established using blindfolding.

Task, relational, and cognitive crafting were shown to explain about 61.4% and 47.3%, of the variance in OC and PJF respectively, with acceptable R^2 statistics (.10) for both (Falk & Miller, 1992). Also, the Q^2 values for Organizational commitment (.530) and person job fit (.458) reveal a moderate predictive relevance of the PLS-SEM model (Hair et al., 2017).

4.6. Mediation Analysis

The study conducted the mediation analysis by following the general guidelines proposed by Baron & Kenny (1986) and the PLS-SEM-specific recommendations made by Hair et al.(2017). The objective was to assess the mediating role of person job fit (PJF) in the association between all the three facets of job crafting and faculty organizational commitment. The results, as presented in Table 6, indicate that PJF had a significant ($p < .001$) and partially mediating role ($\beta = .132$, $t =$

4.269, $p = .000$) in the TC→OC relationship. The total effect of task crafting on organizational commitment was also found to be significant ($\beta = .414$, $t = 7.710$, $p = .000$). Further, the direct effect was still significant ($\beta = .258$, $t = 5.409$, $p = .000$) even when the mediator variable was taken into account. Therefore, it can be inferred that person-job fit (PJF) acted as a partial mediator in the TC→OC relationship. Moreover, the analysis results displayed in Table 6 revealed that PJF had a significant ($p < .001$) partial mediating role ($\beta = .085$, $t = 3.599$, $p = .000$) in the RC→OC relationship. The direct effect of relational crafting (RC) on organizational commitment (OC) ($\beta = .160$, $t = 3.694$, $p = .000$) and the total effect of relational crafting (RC) on organizational commitment (OC) ($\beta = .245$, $t = 5.294$, $p = .000$) both remained significant even when the mediator variable was taken into consideration. This finding supports the conclusion that PJF serves as a partial mediator in the RC-OC relationship.

Furthermore, the findings presented in Table 6 showed that PJF plays a significant ($p < .001$) partial mediating role in the CC→OC relationship ($\beta = .094$, $t = 3.706$, $p = .000$). The direct effect of CC on OC was still momentous when the mediator variable was included ($\beta = .158$, $t = 3.443$, $p = .001$). The total effect of CC on OC was also substantial ($\beta = .252$, $t = 4.940$, $p = .000$). As a result, CC and OC's interactions are partially mediated by PJF.

Table 6 Results of Mediation

Paths	Total Effect		Direct Effect			Indirect Effect			Decision	
	β	P value	Paths	β	P value	Paths	β	T statistics		P value
TC → OC	0.414	.000**	TC----- OC	0.258	.000**	TC---PJF--- OC	0.132	4.269	.000**	Partial Mediation
RC-----OC	0.245	.000**	RC----- OC	0.160	.000**	RC---PJF--- OC	0.085	3.599	.000**	Partial Mediation
CC-----OC	0.252	.000**	CC----- OC	0.158	.001**	CC---PJF--- OC	0.094	3.706	.000**	Partial Mediation

Note: $P < .001$ **

5. Discussion

The outcomes of the present study have provided robust backing for the hypothesized model. The study results have shown a substantial positive impact of task crafting on the commitment of faculty members, therefore confirming H1. The findings are in consonance with the outcomes of already available literature (Cheng et al., 2016; Ghitulescu, 2006; G.-N. Kim & Lee, 2016; Leana et al., 2009). When faculty members participate in crafting the physical precincts of their professions by way of bringing out new methods of teaching, adding more challenging projects, altering the latitude of their job at work, and spending more time on main responsibilities, it increases the meaningfulness of the job, leading to the increase in commitment level with regard to the institution they work for. Leana et al., (2009) also emphasized that engaging in task crafting at the team level increases the satisfaction and commitment of teachers working in various childcare centers in the USA. Also, Lee & McNaughtan, (2020) have highlighted the importance of implementing task crafting in higher education because, through task crafting, faculty members can maintain a balance between various tasks like teaching, and research and service, they have to juggle with. However, the study by McNaughtan et al. (2022) have found a negative influence of task crafting on organizational commitment of faculty members, paving the way for more research studies on this topic in order to bring out clarity in relationships. Regarding H2, relational crafting was also found to have a favorable effect on the commitment of faculty towards their organizations, substantiating the findings of McNaughtan et al. (2022); Noesgaard & Jørgensen, (2023). Drawing on the conservation of resources theory (COR) by Hobfoll (1989), building inter-personal relationships with people at work can turn out to be a momentous resource that employees can use to balance the demands of their jobs and achieve positive outcomes both for themselves as well as for the organization. Regarding H3, the results showed a noteworthy effect of cognitive crafting on faculty commitment level. Employees engaging in altering the perceptions of their jobs in a positive way, like thinking that their job is having a significant impact on the organization as well as society and that their job is giving their life a purpose, it will help them add more meaning to their job and cultivate a positive identity at work, which in turn increases their commitment levels towards their jobs and organization (Wrzesniewski et al., 2013). The findings corroborate the studies of Ghitulescu (2006), McNaughtan et al. (2022) and

Noesgaard & Jorgensen (2018). The current study is also intended to analyze the indirect relations by employing person-job fit as an intervening variable in the relationship among faculty commitment and job crafting. The results indicate that person-job fit partially mediated the association among job-crafting facets and faculty organizational commitment, thus partly confirming H4-H6. The inferences suggest that person-job fit did not completely suppress the impact of all three dimensions of crafting, as the size of the direct impact is much larger than the size of the indirect impact, indicating that all three forms of crafting have a strong influence on faculty organizational commitment. The results are, to some extent, in contradiction with the study of Moulik and Giri (2022), wherein the findings have shown that person-job fit fully mediated the association between increasing social resources, which is crafting relational boundaries, and the affective commitment of employees working in various IT companies across India. However, it is pertinent to mention that the study has taken into account only one dimension of job crafting, which is relational crafting. Further, the study took into consideration commitment only in an affective context. Furthermore, the outcomes also contradict the findings of the research study by Abbas et al. (2022) which demonstrated that commitment (normative, and continuous) and the components of job crafting based on JD-R model among food and beverage employees working in eight five-star hotels in Egypt were fully mediated by person-job fit. The possible reasons for this contradiction could be attributed to the sectorial and cultural differences prevalent in the studies. Also, there is a paucity of literature pertaining to the intervening function of person-job fit in the association among task, cognitive crafting, and organizational commitment, which can limit the generalization of findings to a wider population. However, the outcomes of the current study can prove to be an inception to further unveil the role of person-job fit between all three dimensions of crafting a job and employee organizational commitment thereby paving the way for more research in the future across various cultures and sectors to bring out more clarity on the relationships between these variables.

6. Limitations and Directions for Further Studies

The present study was confined to only faculty members from various universities in North India. Accordingly, to spread the generalizations to a wider population, future researchers should take into consideration a larger sample size across diverse disciplines and settings. Another restraint was related to the data collection method used. The current study's use of self-reported questionnaires to gather data may have contributed to the common method bias. Further, the present study has used convenience sampling techniques that might hinder the generalizations of the results. The present study was cross-sectional in nature failing to capture variations that occur over time, future researchers should conduct more longitudinal studies on the subject in order to ascertain cause - effect relationships and account for variations over time. The paucity of literature on the intervening role of person-job fit between the relationships of task, relational, cognitive crafting, and organizational commitment was also a limitation. Apart from person-job fit, future studies should emphasize on analyzing the mediator roles of other variables amongst the facets of job-crafting and employee organizational commitment.

10. Conclusion

This study aimed to evaluate the individual impacts of the facets of crafting a job originally propounded by Wrzesniewski & Dutton (2001), on faculty commitment working in different universities in Northern India. The study also reconnoitered the intervening role of faculty fit with the job among the three facets of job crafting and faculty commitment. The study revealed that the three dimensions of job crafting played a significant role in increasing the commitment level of faculty towards their job and organization. When employees are given flexibility with respect to shaping their societal, task, and perceptive precincts of their jobs to better fit their preferences, passions, and interests, it can improve their job meaningfulness and identity at work, ultimately leading to constructive organizational results. Job crafting can help faculty members get relief from the stress they encounter when juggling a lot of tasks by tailoring the job according to their needs, skills, and passion. Additionally, the study discovered that the association between job crafting and organizational commitment was somewhat mediated by person-job fit.

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